

In dit nummer schreven:

DRS. W. VAN BRUINESSEN was born in Amsterdam in 1923. He obtained his Master's degree in Economics in 1949 and graduated as an accountant in 1952, obtaining both qualifications at The Amsterdam University. He was admitted to membership of The Nederlands Instituut van Registeraccountants a year later. He embarked on a public accountancy career and in 1958 became a partner of Frese, Hogeweg, Meyer and Hörchner.

Since January 1972 the latter firm, with another Netherlands firm of public accountants, has practised under the name of Klynveld Kraayenhof & Co.

Drs. van Bruinessen was elected Vice-President of The Netherlands Institute of Public Accountants in 1969 and became President in 1970. He is still a Councillor of the Institute.

In 1953 the Institute's Educational Board entrusted him with the training of the Institute's students in Business Economics ("The Theory of Ascertainment of Income and Net Equity"). He is the chairman of the Institute's committee set up to study the European harmonization of annual accounts of companies.

E. BEEKMAN is Senior Vice President Finance of KLM Royal Dutch Airlines and member of the Nederlands Instituut van Registeraccountants (N.I.v.R.A.). Born in 1917 he completed his accountancy studies in 1946. Before he took his present position Mr. Beekman was active during about 30 years in the retail-business as controller and finance director of a department store and of a chain store. Furthermore Mr. Beekman worked in the field of automation for National Cash Register in Europe and he is still a member of the board of the Nederlands Studiecentrum voor Informatica. Recently Mr. Beekman published some books on the subject of value-added tax. During 11 years he was a part-time lecturer in retailing at the business school (N.O.I.B.).

DRS. D. G. VAN TIL, geboren 1924. Doctoraal examen economie aan de Universiteit van Amsterdam, 1950. Accountantsexamen aan dezelfde Universiteit, 1953. Registeraccountant, vennoot van de maatschap Pelsers, Hamelberg, van Til & Co. Examinator accountancy aan de Universiteiten te Amsterdam en Groningen, alsmede N.I.v.R.A.

J. UITERLINDEN, geboren 1920. Lid van de maatschap Klynveld Kraayenhof & Co. Was lid van sub-commissies van N.I.v.A. c.q. N.I.v.R.A. terzake van de onderwerpen „interne controle” en „de invloed van de automatisering van de administratie op de accountantscontrole” en later voorzitter van de Commissie Controle Vraagstukken. Is thans lid van de „Commissie van Advies inzake Jaarverslaggeving” van het N.I.v.R.A.

J. A. BEERS, geboren 1940. Vanaf 1967 in dienst bij Van Dien+Co., Accountants. Van 1960 tot 1967 in dienst bij Hoogovens. In 1960 diploma gymnasium a, in 1966 diploma S.P.D. en in december 1972 accountantsdiploma. De aanvraag tot inschrijving in het accountantsregister is nog in behandeling.

PROF. MR. C. A. BOUKEMA, geboren 1933. Studeerde rechten aan de Vrije Universiteit te Amsterdam, promoveerde te Leiden op een proefschrift getiteld „Civielrechtelijke samenloop”, was werkzaam op de juridische afdeling van de Hoogovens en is sedert 1967 hoogleraar in de rechtswetenschap aan de economische faculteit van de Universiteit van Amsterdam.